

Speculation on the Transformation of EM Self-Energy and the Distortion of a Charge

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The potential energy for a point charge q interacting with another point charge Q , both at rest, is $q \phi(Q, r)$. This result may be used to obtain the self-energy of a charge Q at rest, by considering it to consist of the sum of $q(r \text{ shell}) \phi(r \text{ sphere})$. The sum becomes an integral and yields the result $\frac{3}{8} kQ^2/R$ which is equivalent to: $\int dv \cdot \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E \cdot E$, where E is the electric field in the rest frame.

Now $q \phi(Q, r)$ represents potential energy which transforms as rest mass. In the moving frame, q is the same and still a point, so essentially ϕ transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector. Given that the self-energy is the sum of $q(r \text{ shell}) \phi(Q, r \text{ sphere})$ terms, why doesn't each summand transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector?

We speculate that in the $q \phi(Q, r)$ case, a point charge q is also a point charge as seen in the moving frame, but the $q(r \text{ shell})$ becomes distorted. In other words, even if one were to subdivide the shell into pieces and call each a kind of a point charge, they still take up volume which changes. Thus, it seems that a piece of charge dq becomes distorted in the moving frame and so one does not really have the $q \phi(Q, r)$ as the full energy if q is not a point in both frames. The distortion energy of a piece dq seems to ensure that $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + \frac{1}{2} \mu_0 B \cdot B$ evaluated for $v \ll c$, does not equal $\int dv \cdot \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + \text{velocity} \cdot \text{velocity} \cdot \int dv \cdot \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E \cdot E$, where E is the electric field in the rest frame.

Charge Interaction in the Rest Frame

The potential energy of a charge Q interacting with another q , both at rest, is given by:

$$\text{Potential energy} = q \phi''(Q, r) \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{Here } \phi'' \text{ is the electrostatic potential } kq/r. \quad ((2))$$

The potential energy is considered to be equivalent to rest mass, and given that q is an invariant when seen from a moving frame, ϕ'' transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector. Thus:

$$(0, \phi'') \longrightarrow (A_c, \phi) \quad ((3))$$

$$A \text{ is a magnetic vector potential } -g \nabla \phi, \text{ while } \phi = g \phi'', \text{ where } g = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((4))$$

Given that $-\text{grad } \phi''$ is a force and that A contains ϕ'' , then a single gradient combined with A should yield a force related term. dA/dt may also yield a force because $d/dt \rightarrow -v d/dx$.

Thus, a magnetic field $\text{grad} \times A$ linked with a force $q \mathbf{v} \times B$ (\mathbf{v} is the velocity of a test charge) exists as does the piece $-dA/dt$ parallel in E , i.e. $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial.

All of these features appear because $q \phi''$ transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector and q is an invariant and represents a point in both frames.

Self-Energy

One may use the notion of $\phi = \text{energy}$ and apply it to the self-energy of a spherical shell Q. In such a case, $\phi = k \frac{4\pi r^2 \rho}{r}$ and $q = \text{density} \cdot 4\pi r^2 dr$, i.e. one has a spherical shell of charge interacting with a core sphere. Integrating:

$$\int_0^R \phi \rho \cdot 4\pi r^2 dr = \frac{1}{2} \frac{kQ^2}{R} \quad ((5)) \quad \text{where } k = 1/(4\pi \epsilon_0)$$

((5)) is shown in (1). Alternatively, one may obtain ((5)) using $\text{energy} = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \int E \cdot E$.

In this case, one integrates from (R, ∞) and $(0, R)$ i.e.

$$\text{Piece 1} = kQ^2 \int_R^\infty \frac{4\pi r^2}{r^2} dr = kQ^2 \frac{4\pi}{R}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Piece 2} &= \int_0^R \frac{4\pi r^2 \rho}{r} \cdot 4\pi r^2 dr = \frac{4\pi}{3} k \int_0^R \rho^2 r^4 dr \\ &= \frac{1}{5} \frac{Q^2}{R} \end{aligned}$$

$$(\text{Piece 1} + \text{Piece 2}) \cdot \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{4\pi k Q^2}{R} \quad \text{and } k = 1/(4\pi \epsilon_0) \quad ((7))$$

Thus, $\text{energy} = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \int E \cdot E$ matches the integral (sum) of potential energy terms.

In section 1, it was argued that potential energy is like rest mass and transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector. Why cannot one then take the pieces:

$$q(r \text{ shell}) \phi(r \text{ sphere}) \quad \text{where } q(r \text{ shell}) = \text{density} \cdot 4\pi r^2 dr$$

and argue that these summands transform as a 4-vector? It is true that the amount of charge of a shell is an invariant.

We argue that for a point charge q , one does not need to worry about the deformation of volume and its associated energy. A point charge in the rest frame is a point charge in the moving. Such is not the case for a sphere which becomes deformed. If one breaks the shell into little volume units and calls each one q , then in the moving frame the charge q has become distorted and this should be associated with some distortion energy. Thus, one should not expect $\int dv \cdot \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E \cdot E$ to transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector. There are distortion considerations as well.

In the moving frame, the self-energy is given by:

$$\text{Self-energy} = \int dv \cdot \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + \frac{1}{2} \mu_0 B \cdot B \quad ((8))$$

E and B depend on v/c . If one considers $v \ll c$,

self-energy in the moving frame in this limit leads to a result which is not equal to:

$$\int dV' \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E}' \cdot \mathbf{E}' + \frac{1}{2} v v' \int dV' \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E}' \cdot \mathbf{E}' \quad ((9))$$

This indicates that self-energy does not transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector, even though $q \phi'$ does. Instead of $\frac{1}{2}$ one has $\frac{4}{3}$ indicating extra energy due to motion. We argue that this is linked to distortion energy of the charge.

Rest Mass

We note that a rest mass may also represent a point, so $m_0 \rightarrow m_0 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ does not seem to be due to distortion energy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, $q \phi'$, electrostatic energy in a rest frame, transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector. In the rest frame, one may write self-energy of a spherical charge as the integral (sum) of $q(r \text{ shell}) \phi'(r \text{ sphere})$ terms which have the appearance of $q \phi'$. We thus ask: Why do these terms not transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector? We note that q may be a point charge. Its value q is the same in the moving frame and it is also a point charge in that frame. Such is not the case with a shell. Furthermore, if one breaks the shell into tiny q pieces, then each one is still associated with a volume and not a point. In the moving frame, this volume becomes distorted and we argue that there should be an energy associated with this distortion. Thus, we argue that one does not necessarily expect that self-energy should transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector. We note that a rest mass may also be considered a point, so the self-energy of a sphere or charge is something different as is the distortion energy. As a result, $\int dV' \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E}' \cdot \mathbf{E}'$ does not transform in the $v \ll c$ limit to $\int dV' \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E}' \cdot \mathbf{E}' + \frac{1}{2} v v' \int dV' \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E}' \cdot \mathbf{E}'$. $\frac{1}{2}$ is replaced by $\frac{4}{3}$ in $\frac{1}{2} v v'$ suggesting extra energy which we suggest may be due to distortion energy.

References

Feynman Lecture Notes (Caltech)

https://www.feynmanlectures.caltech.edu/II_08.html#:~:text=The%20total%20energy%20required%20to,inversely%20proportional%20to%20the%20radius.

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